

Exploration on the Integration Path of Short Videos and College Counselors' Ideological and Political Work

Li Tang*

Graduate School of Nanjing University of Finance and Economics, Nanjing, China, 210023

*Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

Abstract: *With the rapid development of new media technology, short videos, featuring intuitive vividness, rapid dissemination, and strong interactivity, have become an important platform for contemporary college students to obtain information and exchange ideas. As the backbone force in carrying out ideological and political education for college students, college counselors are faced with the challenge that traditional ideological and political work methods do not match students' acceptance habits. By analyzing the communication characteristics of short videos and the current situation of college counselors' ideological and political work, this paper points out the necessity and existing problems of their integration, and further explores the integration paths from four dimensions: content creation, communication channels, interaction mechanisms, and team building. The purpose is to enrich the forms of ideological and political education, improve the pertinence and effectiveness of ideological and political work, and provide strong support for cultivating new talents who can take on the responsibility of national rejuvenation.*

Keywords: Short Videos; College Counselors; Ideological and Political Work; Integration Paths.

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1. Introduction

In the "Internet +" era, the way of information dissemination has undergone profound changes. As a new type of information dissemination carrier, short videos have quickly occupied college students' daily lives by virtue of their advantages of fragmentation, visualization, and interest. College students acquire knowledge, entertain themselves, and interact socially through short video platforms, and their values, ways of thinking, and behavioral habits are also profoundly influenced by short video content.

College counselors shoulder the important mission of fostering virtue through education and serve as organizers, implementers, and guides of ideological and political education for college students. Traditional ideological and political work is mostly carried out in the forms of theme classes, individual talks, and lectures, which have problems such as dull content, single form, and weak interactivity, making it difficult to meet the diversified and personalized learning needs of contemporary college students. Integrating short videos with counselors' ideological and political work not only conforms to the development trend of the new media era and innovates the methods of ideological and political education, but also narrows the distance with students and enhances the attractiveness and appeal of ideological and political work. Therefore, exploring the integration path of the two has important theoretical significance and practical value.

2. Communication Characteristics of Short Videos and Current Situation of College Counselors' Ideological and Political Work

2.1 Communication Characteristics of Short Videos

2.1.1 Fragmented Dissemination, Matching College Students' Time Allocation

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Short videos usually last between 15 seconds and 5 minutes, with concise and refined content. This conforms to college students' habit of obtaining information during fragmented time such as breaks and commutes, making it convenient for students to receive ideological and political education in their spare time.

2.1.2 Visual Presentation, Enhancing Content Attractiveness

Short videos combine images, audio, animation, and other forms to transform abstract ideological and political theories into vivid scenes and stories, reducing students' understanding difficulty, effectively attracting students' attention, and stimulating their interest in learning.

2.1.3 Strong Interactivity, Promoting Teacher-Student Ideological Exchange

Short video platforms are equipped with interactive functions such as comments, likes, reposts, and bullet screens. Students can express their views and opinions on ideological and political content at any time, and counselors can timely understand students' ideological trends and conduct real-time interactive communication with them, forming a good atmosphere for ideological and political education.

2.1.4 Rapid Dissemination, Wide Coverage

With the help of Internet technology, short videos can achieve cross-regional and cross-group dissemination in a short time. Ideological and political short videos released by counselors can be quickly delivered to every student, expanding the coverage and influence of ideological and political education. Some studies point out that short video APPs have extended and expanded educational scenarios by virtue of these characteristics in promoting online cultural education in colleges and universities [1].

2.2 Current Situation of College Counselors' Ideological and Political Work

2.2.1 Traditional Work Methods, Unable to Adapt to Students' Needs

At present, some college counselors still adopt the one-way indoctrination-style ideological and political education method of "I speak and you listen", which lacks innovation and interest. This traditional work method does not match college students' pursuit of individuality and preference for interaction, resulting in poor effectiveness of ideological and political work.

2.2.2 Lack of Pertinence in Content, Detached from Students' Reality

When carrying out ideological and political work, some counselors focus on theoretical knowledge, lacking connection with students' practical issues such as study and life, employment and entrepreneurship, and mental health. This makes it difficult to arouse students' emotional resonance and effectively solve their ideological puzzles.

2.2.3 Insufficient New Media Literacy of Counselors, Limited Ability to Use Short Videos

Due to the lack of systematic training, some counselors have little knowledge of short video production, editing, dissemination, and other technologies, and cannot skillfully use short video platforms to carry out ideological and political work. Even if some counselors try to make ideological and political short videos, there are problems such as low content quality, single form, and unsatisfactory dissemination effect. From the perspective of research hotspots in college online ideological and political education under the new media environment, insufficient new media literacy of counselors has become one of the key problems restricting the progress of work [2].

2.2.4 Lack of Effective Supervision Mechanisms, Existing Content Risks

The content on short video platforms is complex, and some bad information such as money worship and historical nihilism may have a negative impact on college students' values. If counselors lack effective content screening and supervision mechanisms when using short videos to carry out ideological and political work, the effect of ideological and political education may be counterproductive.

3. Necessity of Integrating Short Videos with College Counselors' Ideological and Political Work

3.1 Innovating Forms of Ideological and Political Education, Enhancing Attractiveness of Ideological and Political Work

Traditional ideological and political education is monotonous and dull, which is difficult to stimulate students' learning interest. As a new type of media, short videos can present ideological and political education content in a more vivid, interesting, and intuitive form. For example, through microfilms, animation videos, and on-camera explanations, ideological and political content such as socialist core values, patriotism, and excellent traditional Chinese culture can be integrated, allowing students to receive ideological and political education in a relaxed and pleasant atmosphere, thereby enhancing the attractiveness and appeal of ideological and political work. This is consistent with the core value logic of short video APPs in promoting online cultural education in colleges and universities [1].

3.2 Being Close to Students' Lives, Enhancing Pertinence of Ideological and Political Work

Short video platforms are an indispensable part of college students' daily lives. By using short videos to carry out ideological and political work, counselors can deeply understand students' interests, ideological trends, and actual needs, and combine ideological and political education content with students' practical issues such as study and life, employment and entrepreneurship, and mental health to produce ideological and political short videos that meet students' needs, such as short videos on employment guidance, mental health counseling, and academic planning. This enhances the pertinence and effectiveness of ideological and political work.

3.3 Expanding Channels of Ideological and Political Education, Widening Coverage of Ideological and Political Work

Traditional ideological and political education channels are mainly limited to offline forms such as classrooms, theme classes, and lectures, with a narrow coverage. With the help of Internet technology, short videos can achieve cross-regional and cross-group dissemination. Ideological and political short videos released by counselors can be disseminated through multiple platforms such as WeChat Video Channels, Douyin, Kuaishou, and Bilibili, covering not only students of their own university but also students of other colleges and universities, and even the public. This expands the channels of ideological and political education and widens the coverage and influence of ideological and political work. Some studies emphasize that one of the important values of college online ideological and political work under the new media background is to break the time and space limitations of education through multiple channels [3].

3.4 Promoting Teacher-Student Interaction, Building a Good Teacher-Student Relationship

Short video platforms have the characteristic of strong interactivity. By releasing ideological and political short videos, counselors can attract students' attention and participation. Students can interact with counselors through comments, likes, reposts, and other methods. In the process of interaction, counselors can timely understand students' ideological puzzles and actual needs, provide targeted guidance and help for students, thereby narrowing the distance with students, building a good teacher-student relationship, and laying a solid foundation for the development of ideological and political work.

4. Existing Problems in the Integration of Short Videos and College Counselors' Ideological and Political Work

4.1 Uneven Content Quality, Lack of High-Quality Works

At present, some ideological and political short videos produced by counselors have problems such as superficial content, single form, and lack of depth. Some short videos simply list ideological and political theoretical knowledge without innovation combined with students' actual needs and interests; some short videos have rough production, poor picture quality, and bad sound effects, which affect students' viewing experience. In addition, due

to the lack of professional planning and production teams, it is difficult for counselors to produce high-quality and influential ideological and political short video works, resulting in unsatisfactory dissemination effect and educational effect of ideological and political short videos.

4.2 Single Dissemination Channel, Insufficient Promotion Efforts

When using short videos to carry out ideological and political work, some counselors often choose a single short video platform for dissemination, such as only releasing on WeChat Video Channels, without making full use of the advantages of multiple platforms such as Douyin, Kuaishou, and Bilibili, resulting in a limited dissemination range of ideological and political short videos. At the same time, due to the lack of effective promotion strategies, it is difficult for the ideological and political short videos released by counselors to be noticed and discovered by more students, leading to poor dissemination effect. In addition, some counselors do not understand the algorithm recommendation mechanism of short video platforms and cannot optimize promotion according to platform rules, which further affects the dissemination effect of ideological and political short videos. In the era of algorithm recommendation, lack of familiarity with platform mechanisms has become an important challenge for the dissemination of college ideological and political education [7].

4.3 Imperfect Interaction Mechanism, In-Depth Teacher-Student Exchange

Although short video platforms have the characteristic of strong interactivity, in practice, some counselors do not make full use of this advantage and lack effective interaction with students. Some counselors only release ideological and political short videos without replying to students' comments and messages, making it impossible to timely understand students' ideological trends and actual needs; some counselors interact with students, but the interaction content is superficial, lacking depth and pertinence, and cannot effectively solve students' ideological puzzles. In addition, due to the lack of effective interaction incentive mechanisms, students' enthusiasm for participation is not high, making it difficult to form a good interaction atmosphere.

4.4 Insufficient New Media Literacy of Counselors, Needing Improvement in Professional Ability

Counselors are the main body of the integration of short videos and ideological and political work, and their new media literacy and professional ability directly affect the effect of integration. At present, some counselors lack systematic new media knowledge training, have little understanding of short video production, editing, dissemination, and other technologies, and cannot skillfully use short video platforms to carry out ideological and political work. At the same time, some counselors' ideological and political theoretical level and content creation ability need to be improved, making it difficult to organically combine ideological and political theoretical knowledge with short video content to produce ideological and political short videos that meet students' needs. Under the new media background, insufficient new media literacy of counselors has become one of the core challenges faced by college online ideological and political work [3]. In addition, due to heavy work tasks, counselors lack sufficient time and energy to invest in the production and operation of short videos, which further affects the process of integration between the two.

5. Integration Paths of Short Videos and College Counselors' Ideological and Political Work

5.1 Optimizing Content Creation, Creating High-Quality Ideological and Political Short Videos

5.1.1 Determining Content Direction Based on Students' Needs

Counselors should deeply understand students' interests, ideological trends, and actual needs, and determine the content direction of ideological and political short videos around themes such as socialist core values, patriotism, excellent traditional Chinese culture, employment guidance, mental health, and academic planning. For example, the video account "Teacher Xiaoyan Aites You" operated by counselors of Nankai University explores Zhou Enlai's integrity deeds based on the university's history, launches a series of works, and its construction experience is summarized as a characteristic path of "school history resource transformation + situational expression". Under the media convergence environment, the creation of ideological and political content needs to pay more attention to in-depth alignment with students' needs to realize the combination of theory and practice [5].

5.1.2 Innovating Expression Forms, Enhancing Content Attractiveness

Adopt various expression forms such as microfilms, animation videos, on-camera explanations, interviews, and scenario reproduction to transform abstract ideological and political theories into vivid scenes and stories. For example, through microfilms, tell the heroic deeds of revolutionary martyrs to inherit the red gene; through animation videos, interpret the connotation of excellent traditional Chinese culture to enhance students' cultural confidence.

5.1.3 Focusing on Content Quality, Creating High-Quality Works

Strengthen the review and check of the content of ideological and political short videos to ensure the accuracy, scientificity, and ideological nature of the content. At the same time, invite professional video production teams or students with relevant experience to participate in the planning, shooting, and editing of short videos to improve the production quality of short videos. In addition, regularly carry out ideological and political short video selection activities to encourage counselors to produce more high-quality and influential ideological and political short video works.

5.2 Expanding Dissemination Channels, Enhancing the Influence of Ideological and Political Short Videos

5.2.1 Multi-Platform Distribution, Expanding Dissemination Scope

Make full use of the advantages of multiple short video platforms such as WeChat Video Channels, Douyin, Kuaishou, and Bilibili, establish a matrix of counselors' ideological and political short video accounts, and realize multi-platform distribution of ideological and political short videos. For example, the video account "Teacher Xiaoyan Aites You" of Nankai University forms a dual-platform communication matrix of WeChat and Douyin through cross-platform content adaptation, with the highest playback volume of a single video exceeding 100,000. In the new media era, multi-channel distribution is an important measure to optimize the path of college online ideological and political work [4].

5.2.2 Optimizing Promotion Strategies, Improving Dissemination Effect

Conduct in-depth research on the algorithm recommendation mechanism of each short video platform, and optimize promotion according to platform rules. For example, on the Douyin platform, improve the video exposure rate by optimizing video titles, covers, and tags; on the Bilibili platform, increase video attention by cooperating with UP masters and participating in platform activities. At the same time, use the university's official website, WeChat official account, Weibo, and other official platforms to promote ideological and political short videos, attracting more students to pay attention and watch. In response to the challenges brought by algorithm recommendation, it is necessary to improve the dissemination effect by accurately adapting to platform rules [7].

5.2.3 Precise Push, Enhancing Dissemination Pertinence

Conduct classified labeling of ideological and political short videos according to students' grade, major, interests, and other information to realize precise push. For example, push short videos on employment guidance to graduates, and push short videos on mental health counseling to students in need. Through precise push, the pertinence and effectiveness of the dissemination of ideological and political short videos are improved.

5.3 Improving Interaction Mechanisms, Promoting In-Depth Teacher-Student Ideological Exchange

5.3.1 Timely Replying to Interaction, Focusing on Students' Needs

Counselors should regularly check the comments, messages, and private messages of ideological and political short videos, timely reply to students' questions and suggestions, and understand students' ideological trends and actual needs. For common problems raised by students, special short videos can be produced to answer them; for individual problems raised by students, targeted guidance can be provided through individual talks and online communication.

5.3.2 Carrying Out Interactive Activities, Stimulating Students' Participation Enthusiasm

Carry out online interactive activities around the content of ideological and political short videos, such as topic discussions, quiz with prizes, and work collection, to stimulate students' participation enthusiasm. For example, after releasing a patriotic-themed short video, carry out a topic discussion activity of "My Patriotic Story" to encourage students to share patriotic deeds around them; after releasing a short video on excellent traditional Chinese culture, carry out a "traditional culture creative work collection" activity to encourage students to inherit and promote excellent traditional Chinese culture through painting, calligraphy, and handcrafts.

5.3.3 Establishing Interactive Feedback Mechanisms, Optimizing Ideological and Political Work

Establish a sound interactive feedback mechanism, sort out and analyze students' interactive content, understand students' satisfaction and suggestions on ideological and political short videos, and timely adjust the content and form of ideological and political short videos. At the same time, include students' interaction status in the assessment system of ideological and political work to encourage counselors to strengthen interactive communication with students and continuously optimize ideological and political work.

5.4 Strengthening Team Building, Improving Counselors' New Media Literacy

5.4.1 Carrying Out Special Training, Improving Professional Ability

Universities should regularly organize counselors to participate in special training on new media literacy, invite experts in short video production, dissemination, and operation to give lectures, covering content such as short video shooting skills, editing software use, platform operation strategies, and ideological and political content creation. From the perspective of short videos, building a systematic training system is an important link in improving the college ideological and political education system [6].

5.4.2 Forming Professional Teams, Providing Support and Guarantee

Form an ideological and political short video creation team composed of counselors, professional teachers, student leaders, and professional video producers to provide technical support and creative guidance for counselors to carry out ideological and political work through short videos. Team members cooperate with each other in planning, shooting, editing, and promoting ideological and political short videos to improve the production quality and dissemination effect of ideological and political short videos. Under the media convergence environment, team cooperation is an important guarantee for realizing the innovation of ideological and political education [5].

5.4.3 Establishing Incentive Mechanisms, Stimulating Work Enthusiasm

Establish a sound incentive mechanism for counselors' ideological and political short video work, include the production and dissemination of ideological and political short videos by counselors in the performance appraisal system, and commend and reward counselors with outstanding performance. At the same time, provide counselors with necessary time and funding support to encourage them to actively participate in ideological and political short video work and stimulate their work enthusiasm.

6. Guarantee Measures for the Integration of Short Videos and College Counselors' Ideological and Political Work

6.1 Strengthening Organizational Leadership, Clarifying Responsibility Division

Universities should establish a leading group for the integration of short videos and ideological and political work, with university leaders as group leaders, and members including heads of publicity departments, student work departments, youth league committees, academic affairs offices, information technology centers, and counselor representatives from various colleges. The leading group is responsible for overall planning of various work for the integration of short videos and ideological and political work, clarifying the responsibility division of each department, coordinating and solving problems encountered in the integration process, and ensuring the orderly

progress of integration work. From the perspective of short videos, the construction of the college ideological and political education system requires clear organizational guarantees [6].

6.2 Improving System Construction, Standardizing Work Processes

Formulate system documents such as the "Management Measures for College Counselors' Ideological and Political Short Video Work" and the "Content Review Standards for College Ideological and Political Short Videos" to standardize the processes and requirements of counselors' ideological and political short video work. Clarify the responsible subjects and work standards for each link of ideological and political short videos, such as topic selection, planning, shooting, editing, review, release, and promotion, to ensure the content quality and dissemination effect of ideological and political short videos. At the same time, establish a copyright protection system for ideological and political short videos to standardize the use and dissemination of ideological and political short videos and avoid copyright disputes.

6.3 Increasing Funding Investment, Providing Material Guarantee

Universities should increase funding investment in the integration of short videos and ideological and political work, which is used for purchasing short video shooting and editing equipment, building short video production studios, carrying out counselors' new media literacy training, and holding ideological and political short video selection activities. In the new media era, funding investment is the material basis for optimizing the path of college online ideological and political work [4]. At the same time, provide counselors with necessary office equipment and network support to ensure that counselors can smoothly carry out ideological and political work through short videos. In addition, encourage social forces to participate in the project construction of the integration of short videos and ideological and political work, providing more funds and resources for integration work.

6.4 Strengthening Supervision and Evaluation, Ensuring Work Effectiveness

Establish a sound supervision and evaluation mechanism for the integration of short videos and ideological and political work, and regularly conduct supervision, inspection, evaluation, and assessment of the development of counselors' ideological and political short video work. The evaluation content includes the quantity, quality, dissemination effect, and student satisfaction of ideological and political short videos. Through supervision and evaluation, problems existing in the integration process are timely found, improvement measures are put forward, and the integration path is continuously optimized to ensure the effectiveness of the integration of short videos and college counselors' ideological and political work. At the same time, take the evaluation results as an important basis for counselors' performance appraisal and selection of excellent staff, encouraging counselors to continuously improve their level of ideological and political short video work.

7. Conclusion

As an important communication carrier in the new media era, short videos provide new opportunities for the innovative development of college counselors' ideological and political work. Integrating short videos with college counselors' ideological and political work can not only innovate the forms of ideological and political education, enhance the attractiveness and appeal of ideological and political work, but also be close to students' lives, improve the pertinence and effectiveness of ideological and political work, expand the channels of ideological and political education, and widen the coverage and influence of ideological and political work. However, in the integration process, there are still problems such as uneven content quality, single dissemination channel, imperfect interaction mechanism, and insufficient new media literacy of counselors.

Therefore, it is necessary to explore the integration paths of the two from four dimensions: optimizing content creation, expanding dissemination channels, improving interaction mechanisms, and strengthening team building, and ensure the orderly progress of integration work through guarantee measures such as strengthening organizational leadership, improving system construction, increasing funding investment, and strengthening supervision and evaluation. In the future, with the continuous development of new media technology and the continuous changes of college students' needs, the integration of short videos and college counselors' ideological and political work will be further deepened, making greater contributions to cultivating new talents who can take on the responsibility of national rejuvenation.

In subsequent research, we can further explore the application of new technologies such as big data and artificial intelligence in ideological and political short video work, such as realizing the precise push of ideological and political short videos through big data analysis of students' viewing behavior and ideological trends, and using artificial intelligence technology to generate personalized ideological and political short video content to meet students' personalized needs. At the same time, we can strengthen cooperation with other universities, short video platforms, and social institutions to jointly promote the integrated development of short videos and ideological and political work, and form a good situation of collaborative education.

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